

FUNDAMENTALS OF CIVIL LAW

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Annotation: the article reflects the basics of civil law and the leadership of property relations within the framework of civil-legal relations, the basic principles of civil law.

Keywords: civil, civil-legal relations, principles of civil law, norms of civil law.

One of the main goals of the reforms carried out in our country is to create new economic relations based on the laws of the market economy and create a legislative framework aimed at consistent legal regulation of them.

First president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov as noted, "the tremendous work carried out in our country over the past years on the formation of a reliable legislative framework for changes in the field of market economy is no secret to anyone, of course. In recognition of all this, it is necessary to seriously revise most of our existing laws based on the practice of their application and the new real state of development of market relations in our country at the moment".¹

Considered one of the independent and important areas of any system of law in which civil law developed, it arose based on the initial foundation of the system of law formed in the ancient Roman state. All actions committed during that period, initially regulated by civil legal norms, subsequently had a positive effect on the comprehensive development of civil law, an increase in its importance in social life, the strengthening and growth of its position among the spheres of law.

During the years of independence, many laws and legislative acts were adopted in order to fully form market relations in our country. These legislative acts radically changed civil-legal relations both in terms of content and in terms of forms of manifestation. The equality, independence, initiative of participants in civil-legal relations was broadened, the scope of relations legally regulated by civil law was greatly expanded, a number of new law institutions were introduced in property relations related to private property, entrepreneurship and strengthening them, and norms were first introduced in civil-legal relations that had the greatest importance of business reputation, material compensation for moral damage.

"It is clear that I.A.Karimov, - extremely important changes that will be achieved as a result of increasingly deep reforms will never be in one day, at the expense of someone's order or desire. For this, of course, time is needed, the main thing is that the content and goals of these

¹ Karimov.I.A.Mamlakatimizda demokratik islohotlarni yanada chuqurlashtirish va fuqarolik jamiyatini rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisi Qonunchilik palatasi va Senatining qo'shma majlisidagi ma'ruza//T.: "Xalq so'zi",2010-yil 13-noyabr.

reforms are deeply understood and supported by our society, our people, are decisive. One has to repeat – only the support of our people will give strength to any reforms".²

Civil law is one of the main areas of the legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the improvement of economic relations in the period of gradual transition to market economy relations in our country consists in the sum of legal norms aimed at regulating and strengthening property relations in order to more and more fully meet the material and spiritual needs of citizens and other entities.³

Relations regulated on the basis of the norms of civil law differ in their essence and nature from those regulated through the norms of other branches of law. These relations arise between economically and legally independent, non-subordinated parties, which consist of relations in which the value is determined, the commodity has a form of money and, due to this, arise on the basis of an equivalent, remuneration.⁴

Civil-legal relations are regulated and strengthened in our country by a separate sphere of law – civil law. It occurs between a number of equal entities – citizens, legal entities and the state.

Civil law is the sum of legal norms that regulate and strengthen property and personal non-property relations between legally equal entities.

Within the framework of Civil Law relations, property relations occupy a leading place. When it comes to corruption in education, a thousand unfortunately continue to increase as much as it is fought against it.

Property relations are understood as economic relations, that is, social relations in which the means of production, consumer goods, the labor of a person in general are associated with the creation, possession, use and disposal of any products.

Not all property relations are regulated by the norms of civil law. Some property relations are also regulated by other areas of law. Property relations based on the administrative subordination of one party to the other party participating in the legal relationship – are regulated by the norms of Administrative Law, relations related to taxes and budgets – by the norms of financial law, as well as relations related to land – by the norms of Land Law, relations related to the labor contract and disciplinary subordination – by the norms of labor law.

Civil law regulates property relations, which are mainly determined by a certain equivalent (equality), expressed in value, assessment and whose participants are seen equally.⁵

The basic principles of civil law include:

1. Equal rights of the parties involved in Civil Law relations;
2. Equality of all forms of property and bab-fold protection from the legal side;
3. Separation of property relations from ideological relations;
4. What is not prohibited by law is allowed;
5. Implementation of participants in civil-legal relations on the principles of social justice and legality;

² Karimov.I.A.O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi qabul qilinganligining 21 yilligiga bag'ishlangan tantanali marosimdagi "Amalga oshirayotgan islohotlarimizni yanada chuqurlashtirish va fuqarolik jamiyati qurish – yorug' kelajagimizning asosiy omilidir" ma'ruzasi. -T.:2013-yil 6-dekabr.

³ Topildiyev.V. "Fuqarolik huquqi". I qism. "Universitet".-T.:2014.6-B.

⁴ Rahmonqulov.H.R.Fuqarolik huquqi muammolari.-T.:2010.43-B.

⁵ Huquqshunoslik.Noyuridik oliy ta'lim muassasalarining talabalari uchun uslubiy qo'llanma.Toshkent-2016.79-B.

6. Inviolability of the property of participants in civil-legal relations;
7. The fact that no one has the right to arbitrarily interfere with the private use of participants in a civil-legal relationship, without having legal grounds;
8. Unimpeded exercise of Civil Rights (Article 1 of the FK;
9. Restoration of violated rights of participants in civil-legal relations;
10. Ensuring the protection of the rights of participants in a civil-legal relationship through the court;
11. Freedom to contract;
12. Free movement of goods, services and financial resources throughout the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.⁶

⁶ Huquqshunoslik.Noyuridik oliy ta'lim muassasalarining talabalari uchun uslubiy qo'llanma.Toshkent-2016.81-B.

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